

Pairing is the process where you establish yourself as a reinforcer to build a positive relationship with your student. Pairing is an antecedent-based procedure that embeds the environment, therapist, and materials with preferred items and activities in order to build rapport with clients and prevent or reduce the potential aversive nature of the therapeutic context.

Steps of Pairing	What this looks like:
1. Proximity	<p>Definition: BT remains within an arm’s length of the child</p> <p>Example: The BT stays close to the child for the entire pairing sessions</p>
2. Praise	<p>Definition: BT uses behavior-specific praise contingent on appropriate play skills or any appropriate behavior (e.g., child is sitting at the table in their chair).</p> <p>Example: “You are rocking sitting at the snack table with me!”</p> <p>Example: “I love that you are stacking the blocks and building a tower!”</p>
3. Reflect	<p>Definition: BT repeats vocalizations made by client</p> <p>Example: Child: “Choo Choo” BT: “Choo choo! The train goes, ‘Choo choo!’”</p> <p>Example: Child: “I want swing!” BT: “Swing! You want the swing! Here you go!”</p>
4. Imitate	<p>Definition: imitate appropriate play skills exhibited by client (or following the child’s lead by engaging with what they are playing with)</p> <p>Example: Child: *approaches swing* BT: *follows child to swing*</p> <p>Example: Child: *begins to play with blocks* BT: *begins to build and stack blocks*</p>
5. Describe	<p>Definition: BT narrates the appropriate play/functional skills exhibited by the client</p> <p>Example: “You are climbing up the stairs. OH! Now you’re going down the slide! WEEEE!”</p> <p>Example: “You are snackin’ on some Goldfish. And you’re chew- chew-chewing.”</p>
6. Initiate	<p>Definition: BT offers tangible items to client. Avoid taking items from the learner; the goal is to GIVE items.</p> <p>Example: BT: *makes Buzz Lightyear soar in the sky and hands Buzz Lightyear to child*</p> <p>Example: BT: *shakes a glitter-ball and holds up the toy for the child to see* Child: *reaches for glitter-ball* BT: *gives glitter-ball to child*</p>
7. Create	<p>Definition: BT creates new activities by changing the function of the toy</p> <p>Example: BT: *swirls around a water bottle to make a tornado*</p> <p>Example: BT: *sets up tea time for the crayons around a makeshift table*</p>
8. Enthusiasm	<p>Definition: BT presents a manner consistent with enjoyment, approval, interest and “silly” behaviors. Examples include: increasing/decreasing vocal volume, exaggerating body movements, inflecting voice, eye contact with body oriented toward the client</p> <p>Example: The child completes an activity correctly *BT stands up, raises arms, shouts congratulations* BT: YOU DID IT! Let’s go play in the gym! *makes a big deal opening the door and engages with child in the gym*</p>
9. Declarative Statements	<p>Definition: BT avoids placing demands or asking questions</p> <p>Example: BT: “You are playing with blocks!”</p> <p>Non-Example: BT: “What are you playing with?”</p>